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Study on the Implementation of the Total War Strategy in War Against the Dutch Occupation (Pattimura War Case Study)

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Abstract

The Total people's war is essentially a total war for all Indonesians by mobilizing all national strength and resources to uphold state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national safety from other nations that threaten or occupy the territory of the Republic of Indonesia. The Total People's War is characterized by populist, totality and territorial characteristics. The Pattimura War was a war of the Maluku People led by Kapitan Pattimura against the Dutch occupation which took place from 16 May 1817 to 16 December 1817. This war was one of the battles the Dutch had ever fought during their occupation in Indonesia. This study aims to determine the extent to which the implementation of the total war strategy in the Pattimura War in 1817 carried out by Kapitan Pattimura in Maluku by identifying it from the aspects of the philosophy of defense science and total war strategy by using historical research methods and qualitative descriptive research methods with literature study techniques. The results of the study stated that in the context of the Pattimura War, the total war strategy could be synthesized as a total war for all the people of Maluku by exerting all their strength and resources to uphold the sovereignty and territorial integrity and the safety of the nation from the threat of Dutch occupation. Kapitan Pattimura has implemented a total war strategy characterized by populist, totality and territorial in the Pattimura War.

Keywords: Maluku, Pattimura War, Philosophy of Defense Science, Total War Strategy

1. Introduction

The Pattimura War was a war of the Maluku People led by Kapitan Pattimura against the Dutch occupation which took place from 16 May 1817 to 16 December 1817. This war was one of the battles the Dutch had ever fought during their occupation in Indonesia.

Since the 16th century, the spirit of colonialism and imperialism emerged in European nations to seek resources from other parts of the world, including Nusantara, to fulfill their daily needs. Spices that have high economic

value have become part of the international trading community, which is one of the factors for the European nation to dominate the Asian continent. Since then, Nusantara has been used as a colony. Portuguese, Spanish, British and Dutch took turns controlling Nusantara. The natural resources of Nusantara were exploited to enrich the colonial country. Maluku, as a region rich in spices, has long been the target of European nations (Sampono, 2015).

The Dutch occupation of Maluku began in 1605 after successfully defeating the Portuguese and controlling Ambon Island and its surrounding areas. Apart from wanting to control natural resources in the form of spices, the Dutch wanted to control the Maluku region politically. With the politics of divide et impera, the Sultanate and kingdoms in Maluku were pitted against one another so that the Dutch succeeded in controlling the countries in Maluku. The Dutch then conducted a monopoly on the spice trade by implementing various policies that were very burdensome and made the life of the people of Maluku very miserable. This oppression is felt in all aspects of people's lives, both in terms of socio-economic, political and social psychological aspects (Pattikayhatu, J.A., 1983).

In 1811 Britain under the leadership of Thomas Stamford Raffles controlled all Dutch-controlled areas in Indonesia, including Maluku in it. When the British came to power, all policies of the Dutch Colonial government were abolished. During the British rule under Raffles, the Maluku situation was relatively calm because the British were willing to pay for the crops of the people of Maluku. Even Maluku youths were given the opportunity to work in the British army service (Sardiman, 2017). Thomas Matulesy is one of the young Maluku youths who took part in the recruitment and was appointed leader of the Corps 500 with the rank of sergeant major at the age of 34 years. The Corps 500 only lasted more than six years, because in May 1817 this Corps was disbanded by the Dutch (Huliselan, 2017).

On August 13, 1814, based on the agreement of the London Treaty I, Britain handed overall control of Nusantara to the Netherlands in 1815. With the London I Treaty, the Netherlands returned to control the country of Maluku (Sampono, 2015). The Dutch again implemented various policies towards Maluku which were abolished by the British. The various policies of the Dutch government were very burdensome for the people, which resulted in people's dissatisfaction in the Maluku country. This became the reason for the emergence of the Maluku people's rebellion and resistance against the Dutch which became known as the Pattimura War (Huliselan, 2017).

The war strategy carried out by Kapitan Pattimura in the Pattimura War received support from all the people of Maluku by taking up arms against the Dutch. Kapitan Pattimura also made use of all available strength and resources to support the war. The war area that expanded throughout Maluku was used as a battlefield and space for fighting in developing a strategy to face the Dutch. This shows that basically Kapitan Pattimura has implemented a total war strategy characterized by populist, territorial and totality in his war against the Dutch.

To find out the extent of the implementation of the total war strategy in the Pattimura War in 1817 which was carried out by Kapitan Pattimura in Maluku, it is necessary to conduct more in-depth research and investigation of the history of the Pattimura War and identify it in terms of the aspects of the philosophy of defense science and total war strategy using several research questions as follows:

- a. What war strategy did Kapitan Pattimura use?
- b. How was the mobilization of strength by Kapitan Pattimura?
- c. How did the diplomacy work in the Pattimura War?
- d. Who were the winners in the Pattimura War?

2. Methods

This research uses historical and descriptive qualitative research methods, with literature study techniques. The historical method goes through four stages of the preparation procedure, namely; heuristics, criticism, interpretation, and historiography. The data sources used are written sources which include books, documents, and journals related to the Pattimura War incident. The historical method is a systematic set of rules or principles for

collecting historical sources effectively, evaluating them critically and testing the synthesis of the results achieved in written form (Garraghan, 1957).

Qualitative descriptive methods are used to obtain data to describe, prove, develop and find knowledge, theories for understanding, solving and anticipating human life problems (Sugiyono, 2012). The data collection technique used was literature study technique. This literature study makes a systematic description of the literature review and the results of previous research that are related to the research carried out aimed at finding a problem to be studied (Nawawi, 1993). The data analysis used is historical analysis, which is an analysis that uses sharpness in interpreting historical facts.

3. Discussion

On August 13, 1814, the Netherlands and England signed the London Treaty I. The agreement in the London Treaty I that the Dutch colonial assets from 1803 onwards must be returned by the British to the Dutch Government in Batavia. Thus, Nusantara from British control was returned to the Netherlands in 1815. With the London I Treaty, the Dutch returned to control the country of Maluku (Sampono, 2015).

When the Dutch colonized again, the old rules of the Dutch government that were abolished by the British were re-applied, including: 1) Control over the people's clove income through the determination of quotas. If there is excess production, the clove trees must be destroyed (felled) or honggi tochten; 2) Body work by requiring each country to provide male labor as labor for Dutch development projects such as building forts, houses, arombai (boats); 3) Obliging each country to provide arombai (boat) and rowers for the Dutch government in conducting surveillance trips at sea and honggi shipping; 4) Purchasing spices (cloves) at a predetermined price (far below the market price); 5) Kwarto work (outpouring of energy) for each adult male once a week without pay; 6) Must use a travel permit for everyone who will travel to other places (Huliselan, 2017).

To strengthen Dutch military strength in Maluku, the Dutch tried to recruit ex-native British soldiers to join the Dutch army service. Thomas Matulesy refused to join the Dutch military service for strong reasons that emerged from his conscience as a country boy who saw the various injustices and oppressions carried out by the Dutch in his country (Sampono, 2015).

These various Dutch government policies created dissatisfaction for the people in Maluku. Moreover, the Dutch also then imposed taxes on lands belonging to the indigenous people (land rent). This policy is increasingly burdening the people. Monopoly and various oppressive practices carried out by the Dutch colonial government caused suffering to be experienced by countries in Maluku. This became the reason for the emergence of the Maluku people's rebellion and resistance against the Dutch which became known as the Pattimura War. This was proven by the appearance of Thomas Matulesy alias Kapitan Pattimura who on May 15, 1817 together with his friends to lead the Maluku people to carry out a rebellion against the Dutch colonialists. This rebellion was known as the Pattimura War (Huliselan, 2017)

Thomas Matulesy, as a young man who had patriotism, loved his country, then built and aroused awareness among the kings of patih and kapitan in the country of Maluku. The figure of Thomas Matulesy, who has a leadership spirit, made him successful in embracing the kings in Maluku to fight against the Dutch Colonial (Sampono, 2015). Thomas Matulesy received support from countries in Maluku that are culturally, linguistically and religiously different. It is very difficult to unite the countries in Maluku, but Thomas Matulesy can do that. Said Parintah from Sirisori Islam, Kapitan Ulupaha from Hitu, and Kapitan Paulus Tiahahu from Abubu Nusalaut, gave their support to Thomas Matulesy. On May 14, 1817 all the people took their oath and a revolt broke out (Kartodirjo, 1987).

On May 15, 1817 at Mount Saniri, a deliberation was held which was attended by state leaders and 90 leaders from Maluku countries, namely from Saparua, Haruku, Nusalaut and Seram. In the meeting it was agreed by all present, besides giving the title Kapitan Pattimura also had the responsibility to lead the war. Thomas Matulesy

was appointed as a warlord with the title "Kapitan Pattimura" which means to lead those who will uphold the truth. Kapitan is a title for a leader who has great and formidable physical strength (magic) and becomes the head of an army or warlord (Latuconsia, 2020). His experience as a former British military personnel helped forge his career to become an accomplished warlord (Pattykayhatu, 2008). Pattimura is a figure who is very tough, brave, and hard to beat because and is supported by all the people and the small kings of the Maluku islands (Ajisaka, 2008).

Since then the struggle against the Dutch colonialists under the leadership of Thomas Matulesy was known as the "Pattimura War" (Huliselan, 2017). The beginning of the resistance against the Dutch in the 19th century started from Saparua and Saparua had become the center of the struggle. This was because the people of Saparua suffered the most from the Dutch monopoly system. Because that's also understandable why the strongest Duurstede fort was built on a rock hill as high as 20 meters on the coast of Saparua City (Huliselan, 2017)

On May 16, 1817, all the forces of the public army, under the leadership of Kapitan Pattimura, stormed the Duurstede fort. In that war the Dutch troops were led by Resident van den Berg. Meanwhile, the fighters were also led by other figures such as Christina Martha Tiahahu, Thomas Pattiwail and Lucas Latumahina (Sardiman, 2017). The fort was captured and all Dutch soldiers in Fort Duurstede died, including the Resident, his wife and two children who were also killed (Dermawan, 2017).

After Dursteede Fort in Saparua fell into the hands of the fighters, the kings of patih and the leaders of the people gathered and agreed to announce the proclamation of Haria. The proclamation aims to build solidarity and solidity between the perpetrators of the struggle and provide the basis for the people's independence revolution and is a statement that the revolution that took place was a people's revolution that was fully supported by the people (Zachrias, 1984).

Kapitan Pattimura controlled Fort Duurstede for three months, this shows how strong the strength of Kapitan Pattimura troops. The fall of Fort Duurstede in Saparua caused a great stir and anger among the Dutch. Three days later the military leadership in Ambon sent a military expedition consisting of 300 soldiers led by Major Beetjes to retake the Duurstede fort (Leirissa, 2013). These troops were escorted by two warships, namely the Nassau and Evertsen ships (Sardiman, 2017). The Beetjes Expedition consisted of Dutch infantry troops led by Captain Stalman and Lieutenant Verbrugger. Meanwhile, the Javanese infantry was led by Lieutenant Abdulmana. The Marines from the warships Evertsen and Nassau were led by Marine Lieutenants Munter de Jong, Scheidus, Musquiter, Rijk and de Jeude. Also in this expedition, the King of Siri, Salomon Kesaulya and the Orang Kaya of Batumerah. This expedition was quite tough and very proud of the Dutch leaders, equipped with sufficient weapons and supplies (Pattykayhatu, 2008).

The troops led by Major Beeltjes made landings at Waisisil Beach. The Dutch also tried to conquer Kapitan Pattimura's resistance through negotiations at the negotiating table, but they were always rejected by Kapitan Pattimura. In the face of attacks from the Dutch army, Kapitan Pattimura demonstrated his ability as a war leader who understood war strategy. Soon Kapitan Pattimura arranged tactics and battle strategy. People's troops numbering about a thousand people were organized in defense along the coast from Haria Bay to Saparua Bay (Pattykayhatu, 2008). Kapitan Pattimura ordered the evacuation of Waisisil village, artificial mines were installed, residents were evacuated around Fort Duurstede.

When the Dutch troops landed, they thought that there were no Kapitan Patimura troops on the beach and Waisisil Village. When the Dutch troops landed and then entered the village, they were caught in a natural mine trap and received resistance from fire from the Kapitan Pattimura troops who were hiding in the trees. In a short time the enemy forces were pushed back and forced to retreat and flee (Huell, 1835). However, the ship in which he was riding had drifted into the sea so that the Pattimura troops easily killed them, including Major Beetjes. The Dutch troops numbering nearly 200 people were killed, only a few people managed to escape, managed to board the ship back to Ambon.

This victory further fueled the struggles of fighters in various places such as in Seram, Hitu, Haruku, and Larike. Furthermore Pattimura focused on attacking Fort Zeelandia on Haruku Island. Seeing this sign, the Dutch troops strengthened the fortress defense under its commander Groot. Patrols also continue to be tightened. Because the fort's defenses were too strong to be broken, the people did not succeed in capturing the fortress of Zeelandia (Marpelina, 2020). Therefore, Pattimura failed to penetrate Fort Zeelandia (Sardiman, 2017).

In the following days in the struggle against the Dutch, the Nusalaut people led by Kapitan Abub, Paulus Tiahahu and Martha Christina Tiahahu as well as King Titawaai Hehanussa launched an attack on Fort Beverwijk in Sila-Leinitu. The beginning of the resistance, the Beverwijk fortress in Nusalaut was easily captured by the people. All Dutch soldiers were all killed except for a Dutch corporal named Biroe and two Indonesian soldiers who managed to hide themselves. In this struggle, Martha Christina is always involved in fueling the spirit of war (Marpelina, 2020).

A few months later the Dutch made the second military expedition. Facing the second expedition of the Dutch army, Kapitan Pattimura changed his strategy, namely by emptying his troops at Fort Duurstede. Kapitan Pattimura troops pulled out of the fort. When the Dutch soldiers attacked and managed to take control of the fort, they thought they had won, they were caught in a trap because they were trapped in the fort. The Kapitan Pattimura troops then opened fire on the Dutch soldiers from outside the fort. The Dutch soldiers experienced difficulties because the source of drinking water was not in the fort, they had to go out to fetch water from the well, many of the Dutch troops were shot. To save the Dutch troops confined in the fortress, the Dutch then deployed a large military force, attacking the bases supporting the Pattimura forces outside Saparua. The strength of the Pattimura troops was due to the support from the buffer areas of Hitu, Seram Selatan and Ambon (Sampono, 2015).

Kapitan Pattimura and the kapitan of Maluku countries, among others, Said Parintah, Kapitan Ulupaha from Hitu, Melchior Kesaulya, Anthoni Rhebok, Philip Latumahina ignited the spirit of resistance against the Dutch in countries in Maluku, resistance spread to the Hatawano area, Uuw- Ullath, Hitu, Ambon Island and South Seram.

The Pattimura struggle also echoes outside the Maluku region. From the East, Flores and Sumba, Pattimura received weapons and bullets. Bugis - Makassar sailors broke through the Dutch blockade and also helped Pattimura with bullets and foodstuffs. The kings of Bali and Sultan Sepuh from Jogjakarta (Mataram) also blessed Pattimura's struggle. Thus a bond of struggle was created in Nusantara to jointly fight imperialism (Pattikayhatu, J.A., 1983).

The Dutch changed their war strategy by first trying to conquer the rebellion outside the Saparua region, which began with: 1) Hitu Area First expedition, 15-17 October 1817; 2) Haruku, the second expedition, November 1 - 8; 3) Saparua third expedition, 8-12 November; 4) Nusalaut Fourth expedition, 6 - 10 November and 5) South Seram Last expedition, 1 - 5 December (Huliselan, 2017).

Massive military operations carried out by the Dutch succeeded in weakening the strength of the Pattimura troops. With the politics of fighting against each other by the Dutch, the strength of the Pattimura troops was getting weaker. Dutch troops were increasingly operating in Saparua. On November 11, 1817 there was a raid on Kapitan Pattimura and his friends in a house in Sirisori Country by Dutch soldiers who were led by the King of Booi who betrayed the Dutch as a guide. Kapitan Pattimura was finally captured by the Dutch army and put into a detention room on the Evertsen ship to be transported to Ambon. When brought to Ambon, the Dutch tried to persuade Kapitan Pattimura to admit their defeat against the Dutch and would be given ranks by the Dutch government. Kapitan Pattimura remained in his beliefs and ideals of his struggle and was not tempted by the Dutch government's offer.

Kapitan Pattimura together with his followers namely Philips Latumahina, Anthoni Rhebok and Said Parintah on December 16, 1817 were finally tried and sentenced to death physically on a gallows located in the field in front of Ambon New Victoria Fort. The patriotism of Kapitan Pattimura and his followers could not be defeated and

conquered by the Dutch Colonial. They chose to be executed on the gallows as Kabaresi (brave men). This also marked the end of the Patimura War between the Maluku People against the Dutch.

Kapitan Pattimura War Strategy

The Pattimura War was one of the major battles the Dutch had experienced during their occupation of Indonesia. The imbalance of power with the Dutch in terms of weaponry and the number of troops was offset by Kapitan Pattimura through the support of the population and available resources as well as control of geographical conditions and implemented with the right tactics. In carrying out the war Kapitan Pattimura used existing resources. At the beginning of the war, Kapitan Patimura carried out direct attacks against strategic targets, namely Dutch fortifications such as Duurstede fortress in Saparua, Zeelandia fort on Haruku Island and Beverwijk fortress in Sila-Leinitu. This succeeded in paralyzing the power base of the colonial troops. The mastery of the Duurstede and Beverwijk fortresses caused significant loss of personnel and material from the Dutch. Psychologically, the fall of Benteng Duurstede in Saparua caused the greatest furor and anger among the Dutch.

The Kapitan Pattimura resistance was carried out in a decentralized manner throughout the Maluku region simultaneously and sporadically. This can be done because of the help and cooperation of other war leaders such as the attack on the fortress of Beverwijk in Sila-Leinitu which was led by Kapitan Abub, Paulus Tiahahu, Martha Christina Tiahahu and Raja Titawaai Hehanussa (Marpelina, 2020). This made the Dutch have to share their concentration and continue to ask for help to increase their strength.

Facing the Dutch landing operation in Waisisil waters in order to reclaim the Duurstede fortress, Kapitan Pattimura used deception as well as creating an element of surprise. The deception tactic was carried out by Kapitan Pattimura by evacuating the Waisisil village, the residents were evacuated around Fort Duurstede. Artificial mines were installed, about a thousand people's troops were arranged in defense along the coast from Haria Bay to Saparua Bay so that when the Dutch troops landed there were no Patimura Kapitan troops (Pattykayhatu, 2008). The element of surprise was shown when the Dutch troops landed and then entered the village, they were caught in an artificial mine trap and received resistance fire from the Kapitan Pattimura troops, who were hiding in the trees. So that in a short time the enemy troops who were pressed were forced to retreat and flee (Huell, 1835). Dutch troops numbering nearly 200 people including Major Beetjes were killed. Only a few people managed to save themselves and managed to get on the ship back to Ambon (Sampono, 2015).

Facing the Dutch strategy of increasing strength through several military expeditions, Kapitan Pattimura used a strategy of pulling his troops out of the fort and letting the Dutch regain control of the fort to further attack and lock them up inside the fort. The Kapitan Pattimura troops then opened fire on the Dutch soldiers from outside the fort.

Facing the strong resistance of Kapitan Pattimura, the Dutch changed their war strategy by first trying to conquer the rebellion outside the Saparua area by carrying out several military expeditions starting with: 1) Hitu Area First Expedition, 15-17 October 1817; 2) Haruku, the second expedition, November 1 - 8; 3) Saparua third expedition, 8-12 November; 4) Nusalaut Fourth expedition, 6 - 10 November and 5) South Seram Last expedition, 1 - 5 December (Huliselan, 2017).

Apart from using military force, the Dutch also tried to divide the people of Maluku by using the divide at impera strategy. The divide at impera strategy eventually became the determining factor in the defeat of Kapitan Patimura. With the politics of fighting against each other by the Dutch, the strength of the Pattimura troops was getting weaker, the Dutch troops were increasingly operating freely in Saparua. The betrayal of some of the country's leaders in Maluku who sided with the Dutch caused the Dutch to find the hiding place of Kapitan Patimura so that they were finally caught and taken prisoner.

Mobilization of the Kapitan Pattimura Force

Mobilization is the act of simultaneously mobilizing and using national resources which have been fostered and prepared as a component of the state defense force to be used appropriately, integratedly and with direction for overcoming military threats or a state of war that endangers the territory and sovereignty of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (Undang-Undang Nomor 23 Tahun 2019 Tentang Pengelolaan Sumber Daya Nasional Untuk Pertahanan Negara, 2019)

In the perspective of resource mobilization, according to Bob Edwards and John D. McCarthy (2004), it emphasizes the conditions that support the transformation of values into real action and emphasizes conditions that make it easier for social movement organizations to cooperate and compete. Edwards and McCarthy and Zald explain important aspects in mobilizing resources such as support bases, strategies and approaches, relations with the wider community. A social movement is not a closed movement, but has extensive links and networks with other organizations. The resource mobilization approach investigates the diversity of resources that must be mobilized in a social movement, the linkages between social movements and the networks of other groups, the dependence of social movements on external support to achieve success and the tactics used by the authorities to achieve success controlling or engaging in social movements (Edwards, B., McCarthy, 2004).

In the context of the Pattimura war, the mobilization carried out by Kapitan Pattimura was to direct and simultaneously use the resources of the Maluku people according to the strategies and tactics that had been determined precisely, integrated, and directed in the context of dealing with the Dutch colonialism. In the perspective of resource mobilization, Kapitan Pattimura transforms existing resources into concrete actions and emphasizes conditions that facilitate the resistance movement by working with each other with supporting Kapitan as well as with troops from outside Maluku. An important aspect in mobilizing the resources owned by Kapitan Pattimura is the base of popular support and support from other areas outside Maluku.

On May 16, 1817, all troop forces under the leadership of Kapitan Pattimura, stormed the Duurstede fort. Fortress can be mastered (Dermawan, 2017). After the success of capturing the Duurstede fortress, the people gathered and agreed to announce the proclamation of Haria. The proclamation aims to build solidarity and solidity between the perpetrators of the struggle and provide the basis for the people's independence revolution and is a statement that the revolution that took place was a people's revolution that was fully supported by the people (Zachrias, 1984). Kapitan Pattimura also mobilized support from other areas outside Maluku to get weapons and bullets as well as food supplies (Pattikayhatu, J.A., 1983).

To counterbalance the resistance of Kapitan Pattimura, the Netherlands mobilized its strength by withdrawing troops from other regions and carrying out various military expeditions equipped with sufficient weapons and supplies (Sardiman, 2017) to weaken the bases for supporting the Pattimura troops outside Saparua (Sampono, 2015).

Diplomacy Efforts in the Pattimura War

The strength of diplomacy is one of the elements of national power (Morgenthau, 1948), which is then made clear again that the existence of diplomacy is a mechanism used for national interests and protection of national security (Fendreck, 2010). Diplomacy also cannot be separated from the total war, because in this form of war it does not only use military force but also uses non-military power (Abdi & Wijayanto, 2020).

In the Pattimura War, the national definition was defined as the support and interests of the Kapitan Pattimura to fight against the Dutch. If it is said that the Pattimura War used the total war strategy, then of course Kapitan Pattimura also used the power of diplomacy to achieve the interests he hoped for.

The most important diplomacy carried out by Kapitan Pattimura was in the context of gathering strength to support the war being waged. The influence of the Pattimura War spread beyond Maluku. Kapitan Pattimura maintains

diplomatic relations and cooperation with other areas outside Maluku. Diplomacy is aimed at obtaining war logistical assistance such as weapons, bullets and food supplies. Aid came from the East, Flores and Sumba. Bugis - Makassar sailors also helped by breaking through the Dutch blockade to hand over bullets and foodstuffs. The kings of Bali and Sultan Sepuh from Jogjakarta (Mataram) also gave their blessing to Kapitan Pattimura's struggle. Thus a bond of struggle in the archipelago was created to jointly fight imperialism (Pattykayhatu, 2008). On the other hand, the Dutch also tried to conquer Kapitan Pattimura's resistance through invitations to negotiate at the negotiating table, but they were always rejected by Kapitan Pattimura (Pattykayhatu, 2008).

Winner in the Pattimura War.

Regarding victory in a war, William C. Martel (2011) in his book "Victory in War: Foundations of Modern Strategy" states that whether victory is intended as a result or as an ideal, both must be examined at several levels: tactics, strategy, big strategy (Martel, 2011). Tactically victory is a military condition and the judgment is based on sufficiently understood military criteria; military outcomes which achieve their objectives and give one party a significant and recognized advantage over its adversary; can be judged by measurable criteria (ratio of casualties, captured or lost territory, number of sorties flown, tonnage sunk, prisoners captured, etc.). Meanwhile, strategically: public opinion; positive assessment of the post-war political situation in terms of attainment and assertiveness that is recognized, sustained, and resolves the underlying political problems.

The success of the Dutch in breaking the resistance of the Maluku people was inseparable from various actions and methods that were not knightly and inhuman. In addition to the betrayal of the nation itself which is affected by the politics of fighting, it is coupled with a shortage of weaponry. Meanwhile, on the other hand, the honesty and norms of war that were upheld by Kapitan Pattimura and his friends had been deceived by the dishonorable Dutch tactics. As a result, the resistance of the Maluku people was tactical be broken.

After the Pattimura War, the Dutch carried out strict guard against the Maluku people and to win over the people again were given relief in the political policies of the Dutch colonial government. Strategically, this is a form of victory for the Maluku people who were fought for through the Pattimura War. In 1824 the Governor General Van der Capellen personally visited the Maluku region. A new form of politics was specially devised for this region and its people. The people of Maluku began to be persuaded and taken in to be loyal to the Netherlands (Pattikayhatu, J.A., 1983).

Pattimura War According to the Philosophy of Defense Science

Philosophy is the mother of all knowledge. Philosophy can give birth to defense science if it consistently works in dealing with national defense problems consistently. The relationship of ontology, epistemology and axiology can be connected to show the common thread of research and the basis for the formation of indicators for the assessment of scientific works (Halkis, 2020). Defense science is the object of defense which reflects the state's behavior to maintain and develop the sustainability of the country concerned. Defense science is also the science of all aspects related to security on a national scale that are inherent in the objectives of implementing national defense (Tippe, 2016). Defense Science or War Science is a strategic, tactical and technical effort in defending sovereignty, territory, people and legitimate government by means of violence or diplomacy (Halkis, 2020). The science raised in this paper is philosophy with a branch of philosophy of war and a twig of the philosophy of war of the Indonesian nation in the context of militancy and history with branches of military history and branches of lesson learned and strategy.

The Pattimura War was a war of the Maluku People led by Kapitan Pattimura against the Dutch occupation which lasted from May 16, 1817 to December 16, 1817. This war was one of the major battles the Dutch had ever experienced during their occupation of Indonesia.

Thomas Matulesy was appointed as a warlord with the title "Kapitan Pattimura" which means to lead those who will uphold the truth. Kapitan is a leader who has great and formidable physical strength (magic) and becomes the

head of the army or warlord (Latuconsia, 2020). His experience as a former British military personnel helped forge his career to become an accomplished warlord (Pattykayhatu, 2008). The emergence of Thomas Matulesy alias Kapitan Pattimura who on May 15, 1817 together with his friends to lead the Maluku people to carry out a rebellion against the Dutch colonialists. This rebellion was known as the Pattimura War (Huliselan, 2017).

Epistemologically, the Pattimura War was a physical struggle and resistance of the Maluku people to achieve independence and sovereignty and to stop various acts of monopoly and violence by the Dutch colonialists. This effort was carried out with a war that lasted from 16 May 1817 to 16 December 1817 throughout the Maluku region with the support of the entire population and using all available resources through various strategies and tactics under the leadership of the Kapitan Pattimura warlord.

Axiology is the useful value of science, the investigation of its valuable principles. Etymologically, the term axiology comes from ancient Greek, which consists of the word "axos" which means value and the word "logos" which means theory. From the axiological aspect, the Pattimura War has shown the values of nationalism, patriotism and leadership as well as unity and integrity which can be studied and analyzed for further use in facing future threats to the nation.

Nationalism is shown through the principle of the Maluku people as a nation that loves peace but loves independence more. In order to defend their sovereignty and freedom, the Maluku people were willing to sacrifice their souls to fight against the Dutch colonialism. Patriotism is shown through sincerity, spirit of self-sacrifice and an unyielding spirit of Kapitan Pattimura and all the Maluku people to the last drop of blood in order to fight for dignity, self-respect and rights as an independent nation. The leadership values were shown by Kapitan Pattimura and his assistants through their capacity, capability and heroism in directly leading the struggle of the Maluku people using all available resources by implementing various strategies and war tactics that were proven in the early days of the war to defeat the Dutch.

One of the factors supporting the success of Kapitan Pattimura is the support from the people of Maluku. Maluku is known as the land of kings because many countries in Maluku are led by kings (Sampono, 2015). But all of them were united and loyal to support Kapitan Pattimura. This shows that unity played an important role in the Pattimura War. But on the other hand, the difference in the interests of the kings of the country was also the cause of the defeat of the Pattimura War. The Dutch *divide et impera* strategy succeeded in persuading part of the king of the country to betray and side with the Dutch. This resulted in the weakening of the Kapitan Pattimura troops and the peak of Kapitan Pattimura himself could be arrested by the Dutch because of instructions from the traitors.

The strategy and war tactics used by Kapitan Pattimura generally involved the support of all the people, mobilizing the resources they had and using the entire region as a fighting space to develop a war strategy. This shows the implementation of the concept of total war strategy in the Pattimura War.

Implementation of the Total War Strategy in the Pattimura War

The basic thing that becomes the guideline in the implementation of war is belief in one's own strength, not knowing surrender and not giving up or surrendering territory to the opposing party. The belief in victory, and resistance will not stop until victory. War is held with a layered and deep defense strategy by utilizing all national strength and capabilities into the concept of universal people's war. The universal people's war is essentially a "total war for all Indonesians by mobilizing all national strength and resources to uphold state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national safety from other nations that threaten or occupy the territory of the Republic of Indonesia. The People's total war is characterized by populist, totality and Territoriality" (Kemenhan RI, 2007).

Populist is manifested through the participation of all Indonesian people according to their roles, abilities, professions and expertise as a manifestation of the rights and obligations of every citizen in defending the country. Totality is realized through the mobilization of all Indonesian national strength and resources to be able to be mobilized in the interests of facing threats, both from outside and within the country. Territoriality is manifested

in the empowerment of the entire territory of the country as a fighting space in developing a defense strategy to achieve goals (Prabowo, 2019).

The populist characteristics of the Pattimura War were shown by the participation of all Maluku people according to their roles, abilities, professions and expertise as a manifestation of their rights and obligations in defending the country. The war strategy carried out by Kapitan Pattimura in the Pattimura War received support from all the people of Maluku by taking up arms against the Dutch. The participation of all the people of Maluku in the Pattimura War was first manifested in the form of support for Thomas Matulesy to lead the war against the Dutch. On May 14, 1817 all the people took their oath and a revolt broke out (Kartodirjo, 1987). The success of Kapitan Pattimura was due to the support of all the people and the little kings of the Maluku islands (Ajisaka, 2008).

Furthermore, in the war, on May 16, 1817, the participation of the people, which was transformed into a force under the leadership of Kapitan Pattimura, attacked the Duurstede fortress. Fortress can be mastered (Dermawan, 2017). After the success of taking Duurstede, the people of Maluku carried out the Haria Proclamation which aimed to build solidarity and solidity between the perpetrators of the struggle and provide the basis for the people's independence revolution and was a statement that the revolution that took place was a people's revolution that was fully supported by the people (Zachrias, 1984).

The totality characteristics of the Pattimura War were shown through the mobilization of all available forces and resources to support the war. The ability to carry out war continuity is certainly supported by various factors, namely always maximizing strength, logistical support capabilities, weapon support capabilities, knowledge of fortifications and defenses. Kapitan Pattimura transformed existing resources into concrete actions and emphasized the conditions that made it easier for the resistance movement to cooperate with each other's Kapitan assistants as well as with troops from outside Maluku. An important aspect in mobilizing the resources owned by Kapitan Pattimura is the base of popular support and support from other areas outside Maluku. Kapitan Pattimura also mobilized support from other areas outside Maluku to get weapons and bullets and foodstuffs (Pattykayhatu, 2008).

In the face of the Dutch landing operation at Waisisil, about a thousand people were mobilized in defense formations along the coast from Haria Bay to Saparua Bay (Pattikayhatu, J.A., 1983). Kapitan Pattimura ordered the evacuation of Waisisil village, artificial mines were installed, residents were evacuated around Fort Duurstede. The Dutch landing operation was thwarted and Fort Duurstede remained under control. Furthermore, the people's troops were concentrated on capturing the Zeelandia fort on Haruku Island. Because the fort's defenses were too strong to be broken, the people did not succeed in capturing the Zeelandia fort (Marpelina, 2020). Therefore, Pattimura failed to penetrate Fort Zeelandia (Sardiman, 2017).

Facing the second expedition of the Dutch army, Kapitan Pattimura changed his strategy by pulling out his troops at Duurstede Fortress and exploiting the water source outside the fort. The strategy worked. The Dutch troops were trapped in the fort and had difficulty drinking water. The Pattimura troops then attacked the beleaguered Dutch soldiers.

The territoriality characteristics of the Pattimura War were manifested in the form of a war area that expanded throughout the entire region or country in Maluku, namely on Ambon Island and the surrounding islands which were used as battlefields and fighting spaces in developing strategies to face the Dutch.

The success of capturing the Duurstede fortress further fueled the struggle of fighters in various places such as in Ambon, Seram, Hitu, Haruku, and Larike, Nusalaat. The strength of the Pattimura troops was due to the support from the buffer areas of Hitu, South Seram and Ambon (Sampono, 2015).

Kapitan Pattimura and the kapitan of Maluku countries, among others, Said Parintah, Kapitan Ulupaha from Hitu, Melchior Kesaulya, Anthoni Rhebok, Philip Latumahina ignited the spirit of resistance against the Dutch in

countries in Maluku, resistance spread to the Hatawano area, Ouw- Ullath, Hitu, Ambon Island and South Seram (Sampono, 2015).

The Pattimura struggle also echoes outside the Maluku region. From the East, Flores and Sumba, Pattimura received weapons and bullets. Bugis - Makassar sailors broke through the Dutch blockade and also helped Pattimura with bullets and foodstuffs. The kings of Bali and Sultan Sepuh from Jogjakarta (Mataram) also blessed Pattimura's struggle. Thus a fabric of struggle was created in the archipelago to jointly fight imperialism (Pattikayhatu, J.A., 1983).

Based on the description above, in the context of the Pattimura War, the total war strategy could be synthesized as a total war for all the people of Maluku by exerting all their strength and resources to uphold the sovereignty and territorial integrity and the safety of the nation from the threat of Dutch occupation. Kapitan Pattimura has implemented a universal war strategy characterized by populist, totality and territoriality in the Pattimura War.

Conclusion

The Pattimura War was a war of the Maluku People led by Kapitan Pattimura against the Dutch occupation which lasted from May 16, 1817 to December 16, 1817. This war was one of the major battles the Dutch had ever experienced during their occupation of Indonesia.

The strategy and war tactics used by Kapitan Pattimura generally involved the support of all the people, mobilizing the resources they had and using the entire region as a fighting space to develop a war strategy. The war strategy carried out by Kapitan Pattimura in the Pattimura War received support from all the people of Maluku by taking up arms against the Dutch. Kapitan Pattimura transformed existing resources into concrete actions through mobilization to face the Dutch threat. An important aspect in mobilizing the resources owned by Kapitan Pattimura is the base of popular support and support from outside Maluku. The theatre of Pattimura War extends throughout the region or country in Maluku, namely Ambon Island and the surrounding islands which are used as battlefields and fighting spaces in developing strategies to face the Dutch.

In the context of the Pattimura War, the total war strategy could be synthesized as a total war for all the people of Maluku by exerting all their strength and resources to uphold the sovereignty and territorial integrity and the safety of the nation from the threat of Dutch occupation. Kapitan Pattimura has implemented a universal war strategy characterized by populism, universality and territoriality in the Pattimura War.

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